

Effect of Nonelectrolytes on Coagulation Constants of Ferric Hydroxide Sol

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Coagulation of positively charged $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol has been studied in the light of Bhattacharya's equation in presence of a number of nonelectrolytes. The equation has been found valid in presence of nonelectrolytes. The constants of the equation have been evaluated in presence of these nonelectrolytes and the variation in the characteristic constant ' n ' has been employed to compare the stabilising or sensitising power of nonelectrolytes. Glycerol, glucose, and urea stabilise the sol, but ethanol sensitizes it. The extent of stabilisation or sensitisation increases with the amount of nonelectrolyte.

The effect of nonelectrolytes on the stability of the sols has been found to be specific by a number of workers. Kruyt and van Duyn¹ reported that isoamyl alcohol sensitised As_2S_3 sol towards uni- and trivalent coagulating ions but stabilised it towards divalent ions. The charge and stability of selenium sol was studied by Chatterji *et al.*² against reprecipitation by BaCl_2 in presence of varying concentrations of nonelectrolytes. Prasad and Ghosh³ studied the stabilisation effect of glucose and urea on the coagulation of positively charged Fe_2O_3 sol by K_2SO_4 . Ghosh *et al.*⁴ reported that sensitisation was very much influenced by the time of coagulation. Bhattacharya *et al.*⁵ have proposed a relation between concentration of the electrolyte and the corresponding time of coagulation by the equation:

$$c = a + \frac{m \cdot 1/t}{n + 1/t} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where a , m , and n are constants. This equation has been verified by Mushran and Upadhyaya⁶ and Singh and Bansal⁷. Since n in the above equation is related with the sensitivity and susceptibility of the sol to the electrolyte and so it may be taken as a measure of the stability of the sol (with reference to coagulation). Hence an attempt has been made to verify Bhattacharya's equation in presence of different nonelectrolytes during coagulation of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol by KCl ; values of n have been evaluated in each case to compare the stabilising or sensitising power of the nonelectrolytes used.

1. *Kolloid Z.*, 1914, 5, 270.

2. *Ibid.*, 1935, 143, 32.

3. *Ibid.*, 1961, 178, 134; 1961, 176, 29.

4. *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1960, 29, 103.

5. *This Journal*, 1951, 29, 179.

6. *Kolloid Z.*, 1961, 178, 170.

7. *Ibid.*, 1963, 189, 149; *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 85.

EXPERIMENTAL

Time of coagulation of the dialysed $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol, using KCl as a coagulating electrolyte, was determined by Light-extinction method, using a Gallenkamp photoelectric colorimeter and the constants (a , m and n) were found graphically⁸. The values of the constants obtained for the same stage of coagulation, given by the same extinction value for the sol, with and without the presence of nonelectrolytes, are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
Concentration of the sol = 13.44 g. Fe_2O_3 /litre.

	* a (mM/l).	* m (mM/l).	* n (t^{-1}).
A. With nonelectrolytes.			
25% Glycerol (2 ml)	70.0	44.44	27.238
25% Glycerol (1 ml)	65.0	39.21	24.509
5% Glucose (2 ml)	60.0	35.71	23.000
5% Glucose (1 ml)	40.0	33.80	19.147
5% Urea (2 ml)	50.0	31.25	22.760
B. Without nonelectrolyte.			
Ethanol (0.5 ml)	30.0	33.33	20.830
Do (1 ml)	28.0	18.52	13.710
Do (1.5 ml)	18.0	9.09	3.010

FIG. 1

DISCUSSION

Equation (1) may be put in the form:

$$1/(c-a) = (n/m)t + 1/m$$

which shows that the plot $1/(c-a)$ against t should be a straight line and this has actually been observed in the case of sol, both in presence and absence of nonelectrolyte (Fig. 1), confirming the applicability of Bhattacharya's equation for the coagulation of the sol by electrolytes, also in presence of non-electrolytes.

Determination of precipitation concentrations shows that the stability of the sol in presence of nonelectrolytes is in the following order: glycerol > glucose > urea > 'pure' sol > ethanol.

From the values of n it is evident that glycerol, glucose, and urea stabilise the sol, whereas sensitisation is observed with ethanol. The extent of stabilisation or sensitisation increases with increased amount of the nonelectrolyte.